

Yunzhong Jun

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1 PROGRAM NOTES

Yunzhong Jun is a real-time interactive music for human voice and Max/MSP. It is inspired by The Lord within the Clouds in Nine Songs (Chinese name Jiu Ge), which is an ancient Chinese poem series written by Qu Yuan. Yunzhong Jun is also the name of the figure in the poem who controls cloud and rain in ancient Chinese mythology. The lyrics spoken by the performer is come from the poem depicting the scene of ritual in which people calling for rain. The gesture and movement of the performer over the ultrasonic sensors generate the data for controlling parameters in the Max/MSP patch and for manipulating the voice of the performer as well.

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Six pieces of Ultrasonic sensor are used for collecting the data of distance it detected from the palm or body movement given by the performer. Six pieces of Wemos D1 Mini device embedded esp8266 chip are used for data transmission to Max/MSP which is run on the Macbook Pro in the same Wi-Fi through UDP protocol. The data will be converted into OSC information afterwards, so they can be used as the control messages for the Max/ MSP patch. Each of the six ultrasonic sensors has different role of control in the favor of on-site expression. I hope this kind of performance setup can impose a more free expression of this piece and a more possible accessibility to some extent.

3 PERFORMANCE NOTES

The piece can be performed in stereo or quad and 5-6minutes in duration. The composer will provide the performer for Yunzhong Jun. The performer will be on stage, operating the controllers during performance.

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